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**“Poor Feminine Claribel with Her Hundred Songs”: Ballads, Royalties, and the Birth of
the Popular Music Industry in 1860s England**

When Charlotte Alington Barnard passed away in early 1869, notices of her death ran in several major London papers—because although she was a clergyman’s wife from Louth, Lincolnshire, she was also the woman behind the *nom de plume* “Claribel.” Between 1859 and her untimely death, she had written between 100 and 140 songs, primarily in the “sentimental ballad” genre, and those songs had achieved a massive degree of popularity. But here is how her passing was reported in the cultural paper *The Athenaeum*:

Mrs. Charles Barnard, a lady whose pseudonym of “Claribel,” has appeared on the title-pages of many songs, and on many programmes, died on Monday after a short illness. This is not the moment to speak of her compositions.¹

The level of restraint in this small item is palpable. It begs the question—what *was* being said of her compositions? What could possibly be so inappropriate to discuss in the wake of her passing?

It turns out *a lot* was said in the media of Claribel’s compositions during her lifetime, much of it shockingly mean-spirited. In 1866, Henry Fothergill Chorley, the longtime music critic for *The Athenaeum* (and also possibly the author of the above death notice), coined the term “Claribel-ware” to refer to the larger genre of purportedly trite sentimental ballads,² and other publications like *The Orchestra* subsequently took up the word. In general, *The Orchestra* attacked Claribel and her works *con brio*, often characterizing her songs as “trash” or some grammatical variation thereof.³ Anyone who associated themselves with her works, too – her

1 “Musical and Dramatic Gossip,” *The Athenaeum*, February 6, 1869.

2 “Concert-Talk,” *The Athenaeum*, May 19, 1866.

3 “Cakes and Ale,” *The Orchestra*, October 31, 1868.

publisher John Boosey of Boosey and Co., her frequent collaborator Charlotte Sainton-Dolby, even one Miss Jessie Meenan whose 1866 performance of “Maggie’s Secret” was described as an “infliction”⁴ – was subjected to similar scorn.

So what did Claribel do to merit the amount of ire she got? One obvious guess is that she simply had the gall to be a successful female composer in a patriarchal world—and the vitriol she received certainly gives the lie to Derek Scott’s notion that her songs were “acceptably ‘feminine.’”⁵ However, that alone doesn’t explain why she seems to have been the target of press displeasure far more than some of her contemporaries, like the composer Virginia Gabriel or the pianist Arabella Goddard. In a sense, Claribel and her career are a case-in-point for Andreas Huyssen’s notion of “mass culture as woman,” as a threat to the historically masculine-dominated world of ‘high art.’ However, Huyssen’s wording as he explains this concept implies a certain order of operations, a top-down assignation of femininity to mass-culture objects. He talks about “the notion... that mass culture is somehow associated with woman,”⁶ with the word *somehow* bearing a lot of weight in that clause. “Time and again,” he says, “documents from the late 19th century ascribe pejorative feminine characteristics to mass culture,”⁷ as if mass culture had no gendered characteristics before contemporaneous media (for example) assigned it feminine virtues or vices. He also paints all mass culture in this general era with the same brush, by dint of talking about the subject on such a broad level. This generalization is understandable, because his entire discussion of Victorian-era mass culture is a contextual prelude to a much

4 “Concerts,” *The Orchestra*, December 15, 1866.

5 Derek B. Scott, “The Sexual Politics of Victorian Musical Aesthetics,” *Journal of the Royal Musical Association* 119, no. 1 (1994): 101, <https://doi.org/10.1093/jrma/119.1.91>.

6 Andreas Huyssen, “Mass Culture as Woman: Modernism’s Other,” in *After the Great Divide: Modernism, Mass Culture, Postmodernism* (Bloomington, IN: Indiana University Press, 1986), 47.

7 *Ibid.*, 49.

larger discussion of modernism. But Claribel, her career, and the media response to her popularity reveal a different order of events than Huyssen's work suggests: Claribel's works and their larger genre were *already* feminine, and as their popularity skyrocketed during the 1860s, musical and cultural periodicals consequently denigrated them and cast them as low-art at best.

The precise definition of the sentimental ballad—denotative and connotative alike—is worth establishing, as it underpins much of the criticism aimed at Claribel. The departed Nicholas Temperley provides a good overview in *Victorian Britain: An Encyclopedia*, starting with the title of the entry: “ballad (drawing-room).” For that was another name for sentimental ballads, which originated as fodder for middle-class home entertainment—as Temperley puts it, even though they were often premiered by famous singers, “their destination was the drawing room.”⁸ Insofar as women actually *had* power and agency in the Victorian era, the drawing room was the place where they had it – “woman's true kingdom,” wherein she could be a “presiding genius,” as put by Cecil Hay in 1870.⁹ If the drawing room was a space for the domestic, the feminine, the emotional, then it's little wonder that songs like Claribel's fit in there—songs like “Janet's Choice,” in which the title character wants to marry a commoner rather than a laird, or “Five O'Clock in the Morning,” which tells in generalities (but with a bit of a sly wink) of a morning tryst between a milkmaid and a mower. But during the 1860s, the decade of Claribel's career, ballads of this sub-genre escaped the confines of the drawing-room and cemented themselves firmly in public-sphere entertainment, first in amateur public performances and then in more professionalized productions. This is not to say that Claribel's songs ceased to be a vital

8 Nicholas Temperley, “Ballad (Drawing-Room),” in *Victorian Britain: An Encyclopedia*, ed. Sally Mitchell (London: Routledge, 2011), 61.

9 Cecil Hay, *The Club and the Drawing-Room. Being Pictures of Modern Life: Social, Political, and Professional.*, vol. 2 (London, R. Hardwicke, 1870), 40-41.

part of domestic musicianship; the purchasing habits of professional singers alone would not have pushed Claribel's 1859 song "Janet's Choice" into its 20th printing by 1865.¹⁰ Her songs simply found audiences who were appreciative enough to share them in public, as well as in the relative privacy of a drawing-room.

Musical performances in general became much more of a business during this same period, because music publishers of the mid-19th century had been far more limited in their avenues for making money than their modern-day counterparts. This was the era right before the advent of recorded sound—Edison wouldn't invent the phonograph until 1877¹¹—and copyrights were largely still treated only as discrete properties to be bought and sold. Music licensing was a phrase only used in the context of music halls, and in that context it seems to have meant "license to make noise and serve alcohol at the same time."¹² Selling sheet music, ergo, was one of the only ways music publishers could even make money during this period. Publishers advertised sheet music, of course, but the 1850s and 1860s saw the rise of a new marketing tactic among English music publishers, aimed at monetizing performances of their songs in a slightly indirect way: the "royalty system." The concept of music royalties was not entirely new by this time; as Derek Strykowski notes, composers on the European continent had been finagling royalties out of their publishers since the 1840s.¹³ The royalty system that developed in England was singular, however, because it bears much more similarity to modern-day product placement

10 Joyce Andrews, "A Tale of Two Charlottes: Historical British Women Song Composers," *IAWM Journal: International Alliance for Women in Music* 18, no. 2 (2012): 6.

11 Library of Congress, "History of the Cylinder Phonograph," The Library of Congress, 2015, <https://www.loc.gov/collections/edison-company-motion-pictures-and-sound-recordings/articles-and-essays/history-of-edison-sound-recordings/history-of-the-cylinder-phonograph/>.

12 Barrie Francis, "The Licensing of the Birmingham Music Halls," *Theatre Notebook* 70, no. 3 (2016): 170–83.

13 Derek R. Strykowski, "The Business of Composition: Measuring Economic Relationships at Breitkopf & Härtel, 1798–1838," *Notes* 74, no. 4 (2018): 579, <https://doi.org/10.1353/not.2018.0034>.

or social media influencers than to the current music royalties system. Publishers would pay well-known singers to “introduce” new songs at public performances, and in exchange the singers would receive a small fraction of the sheet music’s gross sales,¹⁴ usually around 4 pence for a 2- to 3-shilling sheet in my observations. The singer’s name would be printed prominently on the sheet music cover, and their “royalty signature” (usually just their initials) would also appear.

Music publishers found other ways to make money off performances, too. Plenty of publishers were also concert promoters; a quick scan of the advertisements in, for example, any given issue *The Musical World* or *The Athenaeum* will reveal that tickets for various concerts could often be purchased from music publishers as well as from the venue or the concert organizer,¹⁵ an arrangement which I would surmise involved some sort of commission or fee paid to the publishers. In 1858 Chappell and Co. took the apparently unprecedented step of organizing concerts under company auspices, taking advantage of its part-ownership of the newly opened St. James’s Hall and using it as a venue for what became the Monday and Saturday Popular Concerts.¹⁶ Whether Chappell indeed used those concerts to “[promote] the firm’s music,”¹⁷ as Derek Scott claims but mysteriously does not cite, is a question that could likely only be answered by a comparison of their concert programs and sale catalogs (needless to say, out of this paper’s scope). If reports of the concerts’ success are to be taken at face value, though—one

14 Andrews, “A Tale of Two Charlottes,” 7.

15 See, for example, advertisements in the May 12, 1860 issue of *The Musical World*. Those who would attend Miss Leffler’s concert as advertised could buy tickets from no fewer than four different music publishers.

16 Carlene Mair, *The Chappell Story, 1811-1961*. (London, Chappell, 1961), 18.

17 Derek B. Scott, “Music and Social Class in Victorian London,” *Urban History* 29, no. 1 (May 2002): 60, <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0963926802001062>. Scott also mentions the series of oratorio concerts sponsored by the publisher Novello, but if the records of the Concert Programmes database (concertprogrammes.org.uk) are accurate, this concert series did not commence until 1885.

item in *The Musical World* states that a quarter of the prospective audience at a March 1860 concert had to be turned away for lack of space¹⁸—then Chappell and Co. certainly saw respectable returns on their investment.

Chappell may have been the first music firm to mount its own concerts, but John Boosey of Boosey and Co. – Claribel’s primary publisher – is an equally noteworthy music entrepreneur, because the set of actions he took to acquire and promote Claribel’s music are recognizable as an organized marketing strategy. Popular music in general was a strategic business direction for the firm, in the aftermath of the Parliamentary ruling in *Jeffreys v. Boosey* (1854) that laid waste to the value of foreign copyrights.¹⁹ Domestic composers were thus a safer investment in terms of intellectual property, and indeed Boosey invested a lot of money in Claribel and her career. The first song of Claribel’s that he published, “Janet’s Choice,” was actually first published by George Emery in April 1859²⁰; he clearly bought the song’s copyright at some point before March 17, 1860, when it first appears in one of his advertisements.²¹ “Janet’s Choice” was the first of eight songs that John Boosey would eventually buy from other firms and republish. I have not as of yet found records of these sales with Puttick and Simpson, who presided over scads of copyright auctions in this era,²² suggesting that Boosey specifically sought out and bargained for these copyrights. He also put Claribel on an exclusive retainer. This alone was uncommon for the time, as Joyce Andrews has noted, but it was especially noteworthy because

18 “Monday Popular Concerts,” *The Musical World*, March 10, 1860.

19 Isabella Alexander, *Copyright Law and the Public Interest in the Nineteenth Century* (Oxford and Portland, OR: Hart Pub, 2010), 110-112.

20 Phyllis Mary Smith and Margaret Godsmark, *The Story of Claribel - Charlotte Alington Barnard* (Lincoln, UK: J.C. Smith, 1965), 64.

21 “Boosey and Sons’ New List,” *The Musical World*, March 17, 1860.

22 James Coover, “Puttick’s Auctions: Windows on the Retail Music Trade,” *Journal of the Royal Musical Association* 114, no. 1 (1989): 56–68.

the retainer amount was a frankly staggering £300 a year,²³ over \$20,000 in modern US dollars. In addition, Boosey has been credited as the first music publisher in England to extend the aforementioned royalty system to composers as well as performers,²⁴ making him a forebear of the modern music royalties system—and making Claribel, the first composer in England to have such a royalty arrangement, among the first of a legion of songwriters.

All of this, combined with Charlotte Sinton-Dolby taking up several of Claribel's pieces as royalty songs and publicizing them through various concerts, served to establish a solid music career for Claribel by 1866 – and yet her star still had further to rise. In January 1866, Charlotte Sinton-Dolby announced an event billed explicitly as a “ballad concert,” the first of its kind, at which she sang Claribel's “I Cannot Sing the Old Songs” and “Maggie's Secret” (both of which bear her royalty signature on their sheet music). Multiple news items in the days following the concert attest to the massive crowds, multiple encores, and abundance of applause.²⁵ Sinton-Dolby would not mount another ballad concert at St. James's Hall until December of that year, but *The Athenaeum* made a reference to her “touring” with that concert,²⁶ and 1866 as a whole saw an exploding number of ballad concerts – a whole summer's worth of them at the Crystal Palace, as well as events put on by Alfred Mellon and Edwin Ransford.²⁷ Though this collaboration was not explicitly spelled out at first, William Boosey credits the ballad-concert idea to “the outcome of a chat between Madame Sinton-Dolby and John Boosey,” and indeed

23 Andrews, “A Tale of Two Charlottes,” 7.

24 The two sources that credit him are Mair, *The Chappell Story* and William Boosey (John Boosey's nephew and adopted son), in *Fifty Years of Music* (London: Ernest Benn Limited, 1931).

25 Of which just two are “St. James's Hall,” *The Morning Post*, January 9, 1866; and “Opera and Concerts,” *The Illustrated Times*, January 13, 1866.

26 “Ballad Concert, St. James's Hall,” *The Musical World*, December 15, 1866; “Musical and Dramatic Gossip,” *The Athenaeum*, February 24, 1866.

27 “Mr. Ransford's Concert,” *The Morning Herald*, October 31, 1866.

when the *Morning Herald* claimed that Sainton-Dolby “took the hint” for ballad concerts from Edwin Ransford, the elder Boosey wrote to the *Herald* to correct the record.²⁸

Boosey – and by extension, Claribel – stepped even further into the spotlight in 1867, with the announcement at the end of March of a new series of ballad concerts, “under the direction of Mr. John Boosey.”²⁹ Clearly Boosey, at least, was undaunted by the new viciousness against Claribel that *The Orchestra* had uncorked as of January 12, shortly after its New Year’s champagne. In an op-ed titled “Royalties and Claribel,” the unnamed writer rails against the “inferior productions” bolstered by the royalty system and provides Claribel as his only example.³⁰ *The Orchestra* was not pleased about John Boosey’s ballad concerts, either, predicting dourly that “in the musical sandwich the true balladic ham will doubtless be decreased, bit by bit, and the Claribel mustard augmented, until the latter condiment constitutes the entire article.”³¹

It’s perhaps impossible to tell precisely how much larger the sentimental-ballad fandom (for lack of a better word) became over this decade, but the audience for such music certainly took on new and larger forms. A ballad of Claribel’s could be consumed in a variety of ways, from unobtrusive to incredibly noticeable: by the individual sheet-music buyer practicing the piano, by smaller groups in domestic drawing-rooms or at amateur concerts, and eventually in massive public concerts. Quite simply, as Claribel’s music reached larger stages, Claribel and the femininity inherent in her works became harder to ignore. Andreas Huyssen, in “Mass Culture as Woman,” brings in Stuart Hall’s image of the masses “‘rattling at the gate’” to assert what Hall didn’t: that these masses were “women, knocking at the door of a male-dominated culture.”³²

28 William Boosey, *Fifty Years of Music*, 15; “The First Ballad Concert,” *The Musical World*, November 11, 1866.

29 Advertisement, *The Musical World*, March 30, 1867.

30 “Royalties and ‘Claribel,’” *The Orchestra*, January 12, 1867.

31 “The Music Publisher as Concert Director,” *The Orchestra*, April 20, 1867.

32 Huyssen, “Mass Culture as Woman,” 47.

This is exactly what some prominent musical tastemakers (or gatekeepers) in the periodical press, the writers who referred derisively to Claribel's fans as "the simpering misses,"³³ were so afraid of. The rhetoric that appeared in *The Orchestra*, *The Athenaeum*, and other publications is precisely the reaction to mass-cultural influence that Huyssen describes, of "stak[ing] out... territory by fortifying the boundaries between genuine art and inauthentic mass culture."³⁴

To be certain, periodical-press attempts to define what sorts of expressions qualified as art did not begin as a response to Claribel's work. In fact, the sentimental ballad genre as a whole did not always provoke the degree of media scorn that it did in Claribel's era. One music review in an 1853 issue of *The Musical World* notes that the song at hand is indeed a sentimental ballad, but unlike "the mawkish school" thereof.³⁵ Even before Claribel's songwriting career began, press discourse drew a distinction (however clearly or poorly defined) between appropriate and inappropriate levels or types of sentiment in balladry. Especially after 1866, however, outlets like *The Athenaeum* and especially *The Orchestra* basically ceased subdividing the sentimental ballad genre into its good and bad parts, instead characterizing the lot as base. *The Orchestra's* protestations included, curiously, another food analogy, comparing Boosey & Co. to a pie shop that markets the "One-Pie-Only manufactured by Claribel."³⁶ *The Athenaeum*, generally less vivid in its language, nonetheless complained in December 1867 that "Claribel-ware is becoming a nuisance" and "interferes so largely... with the serious pursuits of artists."³⁷ These are just two among a host of condemnations.

33 "London, January 9, 1869," *The Orchestra*, January 9, 1869.

34 Huyssen, "Mass Culture as Woman," 53.

35 "'You Ask Me Why I Sigh'," *The Musical World*, May 7, 1853.

36 "Reviews," *The Orchestra*, December 14, 1867.

37 "Musical and Dramatic Gossip," *The Athenaeum*, December 14, 1867.

To quantify the Claribel discourse at least somewhat, I examined all the periodical scans I have accumulated and classified every distinct description I found of her music as positive, negative, or neutral/unclear. The periodicals represented here come from a few databases. ProQuest’s British Periodicals has more specialized, in-depth cultural publications that were almost always based in London (e.g. *The Musical World* and *The Athenaeum*). Gale’s 19th Century British Newspapers is particularly rich in regional newspapers, which provided some sense of Claribel’s reputation outside of London, and 19th Century UK Periodicals netted some results from women’s magazines. The archive of *The Illustrated London News* has a small number of items represented as well (most of its search results were advertisements). The results are shown in figure 1 below.

Figure 1

Some quick numbers, in a bullet list for easier reading:

- **Total sample size** is **319** discrete word or phrase descriptions...
- ...across **144 unique articles**, reviews, bits of gossip, etc. (I'll refer to them as articles for simplicity's sake.)
- **Negative descriptions** totaled **111 across 63 articles**, or about **35%** of the total.
- **Positive descriptions** totaled **193 across 72 articles**, or about **60.5%**.
- There were also 15 descriptions wherein either the word or phrase was decidedly neutral, or I could not conclusively interpret the author's tone.
- I began my search with papers from April 1859, because that's when Claribel published her first crop of songs. I found no applicable descriptions, however, until December 1860 – and furthermore, all of the descriptions from 1860 are from one rather detailed piece in *The London Review*.

Figure 2, below, isolates the positive and negative descriptions and adds trendlines. The massive uptick in negative descriptions is even more obvious here, and it also coincides roughly with the advent of ballad concerts.

Figure 2

Figure 3 is an overview of frequently used words or phrases across all types of descriptions. “Claribel-ware,” Henry Fothergill Chorley’s insulting shorthand for the whole sentimental-ballad genre, comes out in front with 16 mentions. The other major insult is *The Orchestra's* favorite, “trash” or some variation thereof; my accounting also included “trashy effusions.” Every other item, however, is entirely or mostly positive in context, even “simple”; 11 out of the 13 occurrences I counted were positive descriptions, and the other two were neutral or unclear. “Simple” is also one of only two descriptors here that addresses the substance of Claribel's songs – because, as Claribel’s prior biographer Phyllis Smith noted, simple music was much more accessible for domestic music-making.³⁸

Word or phrase	Occurrences
Claribel-ware	16
“pretty” and variants	16
simple	13
popular	11
“trash” and variants	9
melody, in some form	9
charm	6
expressive	6
grace	5
pleasing	5

Figure 3

The last major point to address is geography. To hear *The Athenaeum* and *The Orchestra* tell it, the majority of the British populace either already despised Claribel or was slowly yet surely turning against her. However, the vast majority of both positive and negative descriptions in this dataset appeared in London-based periodicals—81.9% for positive descriptions, and 87.4% for negative descriptions. The maps in Figures 4 and 5 also indicate that positive descriptions of Claribel’s music had a considerably wider geographical range than negative descriptions (respectively), although more data will of course beget far more precision.

³⁸ Smith and Godsmark, *The Story of Claribel*, 74.

Figure 4: positive descriptions

Figure 5: negative descriptions

Overall, anti-Claribel fervor seems to have been primarily the obsession of London cultural critics, while people outside the metropole mostly just carried on performing Claribel's songs at their musical-society and charity concerts and sundry. I make no pretensions to the results shown here being definitive or complete. I do maintain, however, that these patterns lend credence and some amount of hard data to Huyssen's "mass culture as woman" notion, *and* to the more complex version of that notion that Claribel's story embodies.

Drawing-room ballads as a genre were arguably never meant to be a form of mass culture, but that didn't stop them from achieving massive popularity. Artists like Claribel, in essence, took these ballads out of the drawing room and put them and their brimming sentiments on the public stage, in the public view. As such, the vitriol of her critics likely stemmed in large part from a perception that she and her fellow balladeers broke the social contract by daring to bring this music out of its appointed place in the domestic sphere. Even the most vociferous of detractors, though, ultimately couldn't quash Claribel's popularity during (and some years beyond) her lifetime—which, in turn, suggests that the strictures and strata supposedly governing Victorian life and culture were not nearly as infallible as they may have seemed.

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